

Proposed Omnichannel Strategy to Increase Sales Revenue in a Fashion Retail Company (Case: La Omvi)

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ABSTRACT: In recent years, the creative industry sub-sector of the fashion sector in Indonesia has become a profitable industry. The development of the fashion industry in Indonesia has contributed significantly, and the creative industry sub-sector group has become a leading sub-sector group. La Omvi, a fashion retail store brand established in December 2020, has experienced stagnation in sales. Due to its small population and predominately immigrant demographic, the Cikarang market has a limited range of products. This research aims to propose an effective omnichannel approach tailored to the specific needs and market conditions of La Omvi, with a focus on increasing sales revenue and enhancing the customer experience. The research employs qualitative methods, including in-depth interviews and observational analysis, to gather insights into customer experiences and expectations. Based on these findings, recommendations are provided to enhance the omnichannel strategy and drive sales growth for La Omvi. This research contributes to the understanding of effective omnichannel strategies in the fashion retail industry and provides practical insights for fashion retailers aiming to optimize their sales revenue through an omnichannel approach.

KEYWORDS: fashion retail, streetwear, marketing mix, omnichannel, customer experience

INTRODUCTION

Fashion is no longer just a primary need, but has become an artistic need, so that it is able to encourage growth in the Creative Industries sub-sector in the fashion sector (CNBC Indonesia, 2019). Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS) (2022) noted that the gross domestic product (GDP) atas dasar harga konstan (ADHK) in the textile and apparel industry increased by 13.74%, which is IDR 35.17 trillion from the previous year. The creative industry sub-sector in the fashion sector has become a profitable industry in Indonesia in recent years, the development of the fashion industry in Indonesia has contributed greatly and has become a leading sub-sector group (Bekraf, 2019). Based on the data of the trend, the performance of the textile and apparel industry continues to experience a strengthening trend after being depressed in quarter I/2020 to quarter III/2021. This indicates that the textile and apparel industry has recovered from the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic, as shown in the image below:

Figure 1 Textile and Apparel Industry GDP Q2 2020 to Q2 2022

Source: BPS, 2022

One type of fashion that is on the rise in Indonesia is streetwear. Streetwear itself is a type of fashion that originally came from the skate, surf and hip-hop communities on the East and West Coast of America around the 1980s to the 1990s. At that time streetwear became a sign for those who use their products to be involved in a movement that is outside the fashion industry (Vice, 2018). This movement was a protest from workers at that time, because it was expensive for them to look stylish, therefore streetwear became a solution for them to look stylish at an affordable price (Glitzmedia, 2020). In the early 70s, sportswear labels such as Adidas, Fila and Dr. Martens are a source of inspiration for streetwear styles. Flourishing into the 80s, surfboard designer Shawn Stussy began selling printed t-shirts featuring their logo. Not only selling skateboards and t-shirts with pictures, Stussy also created a different market at that time, where he limited sales of his clothes, causing a trend of exclusivity among streetwear fans, as informed by Complex Magazine (2011). Over time, more and more streetwear fashion labels have grown. Even in the late 90s, famous rappers also opened their own streetwear fashion labels.

The development of streetwear in Indonesia itself has been increasing lately, especially in the capital city. The rise of local streetwear brands has changed the fashion trend of young Indonesians. According to the Ministry of Industry (2020), Indonesia has the potential to create many global brands, supported by a large population with a growing middle class, a lifestyle that tends to be consumptive, and an increasing awareness of using domestically made products, local brands. have the opportunity to succeed in the international market after building a strong brand image in the country. In a survey conducted by Hypebeast media in 2019, 62% of respondents admitted that streetwear is one of the clothes that never goes out of style.

La Omvi, a streetwear fashion retailer located in Jababeka, Cikarang, has experienced stagnation in sales despite initial enthusiasm from the local community, particularly among young consumers. The scope of the Cikarang market is limited due to its small population and a predominantly immigrant demographic (Pojoksatu, 2022). Furthermore, La Omvi's current marketing initiatives, such as advertising campaigns and web marketing initiatives, have not significantly increased sales. To address these challenges and revitalize sales performance, there is a pressing need for La Omvi to develop and implement a comprehensive omnichannel strategy. This research aims to propose an effective omnichannel approach tailored to the specific needs and market conditions of La Omvi, with a focus on increasing sales revenue and enhancing customer experience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Omnichannel Retailing

Omnichannel retailing is a multichannel approach to sales and customer support that aims to deliver a smooth and integrated shopping experience across all channels, including physical locations, online platforms, and mobile devices (Verhoef, Kannan, & Inman, 2015). According to a Deloitte report from 2021, as customers seek a more frictionless and customized purchasing experience, omnichannel retailing has moved from being a luxury to a necessity for fashion retailers in the post-pandemic period. In order to maximize both channel performance and customer experience, omni-channel management is defined as the coordinated management of the many accessible customer touchpoints and channels. Thus, it has recognised the simultaneous usage of the many channels and their interaction (Verhoef et al., 2015).

Omnichannel marketing goes beyond multichannel marketing by combining various channels to give a seamless and consistent customer experience. Multichannel marketing concentrates on offering many channels for consumer engagement. In a multichannel approach, a business interacts with customers and facilitates transactions across a variety of different channels. Each channel runs autonomously and may have its own plans, objectives, and procedures. For instance, a business may have a physical location, an online store, and a mobile app, but these channels may not be connected, and the consumer experience may differ between channels (Kotler, 2021).

The goal of an omnichannel strategy is to create a unified, integrated customer experience across all channels. It places a focus on the coordination and coherence of communications, branding, and client interactions across channels. The customer's buying experience remains uninterrupted when switching between channels thanks to an omnichannel strategy. Customers may have a consistent experience across all touchpoints thanks to the integrated channels (Kotler, 2021).

Impact of Omnichannel Strategy on Sales:

Omnichannel strategies can significantly impact sales and customer satisfaction in the fashion retail industry. For example, a study by Ramanathan and Ramanathan (2017) discovered that a fashion retailer's sales increased by 60% as a result of an integrated omnichannel strategy. Li and Kannan (2014) discovered that business using an omnichannel strategy had higher levels of client loyalty

and higher sales. Multichannel consumers, who interact with both physical stores and online platforms, tend to have a higher purchase frequency and higher spending levels (Juaneda et al., 2016). Furthermore, Kim and Lennon (2018) highlighted the importance of personalized recommendations and improved customer engagement in driving sales through omnichannel strategies.

Key Elements of an Effective Omnichannel Strategy:

1. **Seamless Shopping Experience**
It's critical to offer customers a smooth experience across different channels. A customer's buying experience should be able to start on one channel and smoothly move to another. This necessitates a unified view of consumer data, consistent pricing, and integrated inventory management (Verhoef et al., 2015)
2. **Personalization and Customer Engagement**
Customizing recommendations and interacting with customers on a personal level can have a big impact on sales. In order to provide relevant product recommendations and promotions, personalization can be performed by using consumer data, such as browsing activity, purchase history, and preferences (Berman and Evans, 2020).
3. **Data-Driven Insight**
Fashion retail businesses can learn important things about the behavior and preferences of their customers by utilizing data analytics. By using this data to optimize sales performance through inventory management, pricing strategies, and targeted marketing efforts Juaneda et al., 2016).
4. **Cross-Channel Promotions**
Customers are encourage to interact with the brand in various ways through coordinated promotions and incentives across channels. Offering exclusive discount or rewards for in-store purchase by customers who interact with the brand online can drive additional sales (Kim and Lennon, 2018).

Customer Path 5A

Customer journey mapping is a tool used by businesses to understand and improve the experience of their customers. It involves creating a visual representation of the steps customers take when interacting with a business, from initial awareness to post-purchase evaluation (Kietzman, 2018). Customer journey mapping, based on Hermawan Kartajaya's 5A framework, is a strategic tool used to visualize and understand the customer's experience and interactions with a brand throughout their entire journey. It allows businesses to gain insights into the customer's perspective, identify pain points, and identify opportunities for improving customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The 5A framework, consists of the following stages in the customer journey:

1. **Awareness:** This stage focuses on how customers become aware of the brand or product. It includes various touch points such as advertising, word-of-mouth, social media, or online search.
2. **Appeal:** In this stage, the brand aims to appeal to the customer's needs and preferences. It involves showcasing unique selling points, brand positioning, and communication strategies to create interest and desire.
3. **Ask:** The "Ask" stage involves the customer seeking information and asking questions about the brand or product. This may include browsing the website, contacting customer support, reading reviews, or seeking recommendations from friends or online communities.
4. **Act:** This stage represents the point of purchase or conversion. It includes the customer making a decision to buy the product or engage with the brand. This may occur online or in a physical store, depending on the sales channels available.
5. **Advocate:** The final stage focuses on customer advocacy and loyalty. Satisfied customers become brand advocates who promote the brand through positive word-of-mouth, reviews, referrals, and social media engagement.

Customer journey mapping based on the 5A framework involves visually representing each stage of the customer journey, along with the customer's emotions, touchpoints, and key interactions. This mapping allows businesses to identify pain points or areas where the customer experience can be improved. It helps in aligning marketing and communication strategies, optimizing sales channels, and delivering a seamless and consistent customer experience across all touchpoints.

Customer Relationship Management

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) refers to the practices, strategies, and technologies used by a company to manage and analyze customer interactions and data throughout the customer lifecycle with the goal of improving customer retention, loyalty,

and satisfaction, and ultimately driving sales growth and profitability (Buttler et al., 2019). This includes managing customer data, identifying and segmenting customers, developing targeted marketing campaigns, providing personalized customer service and support, and analyzing customer behavior and feedback to continually improve the customer experience.

In essence, CRM is about building strong and lasting relationships with customers by understanding their needs and preferences and using that knowledge to provide a seamless and personalized experience across all touchpoints and channels. This can involve a combination of human interactions and automated processes, with the goal of making every customer feel valued, heard, and appreciated (Chen & Popovich, 2003).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection Method

The practice of obtaining information or data from numerous sources is known as data collection. There are numerous ways to gather data, depending on the research questions, goals, and setting (Flower et al., 2009). There are various data collection methods that can be used for qualitative research, depending on the research questions, objectives, and context. The data used in this study are primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained from interviews with customers, and secondary data was obtained from observations results.

1. In Depth Interview
Conduct semi formal interviews with important stakeholders, such as customers, store managers, salespeople, and marketing specialists. Discover their views, experiences, and impressions of the omnichannel strategy, as well as what they expect from it and how it will affect sales. Inquisitive inquiries might explore subjects including shopping preferences, online and offline integration, consumer happiness, and the function of multiple touchpoints in the purchasing process.
2. Observation
Conducting observations in fashion retail stores or online platforms can provide firsthand insights into the implementation and effectiveness of the omnichannel strategy. It is possible to observe customer habits, interactions with salespeople, use of digital platforms, and general customer experiences. To record significant findings, patterns, and background knowledge, thorough field notes should be taken throughout observations.
3. Expert Interviews
Interview with academics, professionals, or industry experts who have knowledge of omnichannel marketing methods and the fashion retail business. In light of their experience, seek out their thoughts, viewpoints, and suggestions. These interviews may offer alternative perspectives, contribute to the knowledge base, and support the validity of the suggested course of action.

Data Analysis Method

The author uses qualitative research methods in this study. Qualitative research is a research method that aims to gain an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon, such as human behavior, experiences, and attitudes and observations of consumer interactions, behaviors, and experiences are systematically recorded during in-store visits, online interactions, and other interactions. Data is collected, analyzed, and interpreted iteratively with both methods. The triangulation of findings from in-depth interviews and observational analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior, requirements, and expectations. This comprehensive analysis serves as the foundation for developing the proposed omnichannel strategy and making data-driven suggestions to increase La Omvi's sales revenue.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

External Analysis

Customer Analysis

Customer analysis is the act of comprehending and extrapolating customer behavior in order to pinpoint the needs, desires, driving forces, and purchasing tendencies of the target market. Customer analysis seeks to learn about the characteristics, preferences, and behaviors of the target market in order to develop successful marketing strategies. Customer analysis include gathering information about and assessing factors such as demographics, psychographics, lifestyle, attitudes, and behavior patterns. Market segmentation, customer group targeting, and consumer-friendly marketing communications are all made possible by customer analysis data. Consumer studies' ultimate objective is to create a value proposition that meets the needs and preferences of the target market and

encourages fruitful customer relationships (Kotler, 2017). Customer analysis will be carried out using primary data from in-depth interviews.

The number of valid sources for a qualitative research consists of a minimum of 5 people (Creswell, 2014). To obtain data from customers, in-depth interviews were conducted with 7 people, consisting of 5 customers, 1 management, and 1 industry expert with an age range of 20-35 years. The respondents were asked questions about three indicators: marketing mix, customer experience, and omnichannel retailing.

La Omvi's targeted customers are people with middle-class and affluent consumer social status who live in Jabodetabek, Bandung, Makassar, Bali, Balikpapan, Lampung, and Surabaya. They are between the ages of 18 and 40 and represent a wide demographic profile. These customers are fashion-conscious and seek current streetwear fashion items that express their originality and personal style. They value brands that provide one-of-a-kind and exclusive products, as well as great customer service.

According to market research and customer profiling, La Omvi's target market are extremely involved with multiple sales channels, such as physical stores, e-commerce platforms, and mobile applications. They prefer simplicity and seamless buying experiences, and they anticipate consistent brand presence and individualized interactions across channels. These are tech-savvy clients who rely primarily on digital channels for product discovery, promotions, and social connections.

Furthermore, factors such as product quality, cost, brand reputation, and overall shopping experience influence their purchasing decisions. They value tailored advice and value-added services that improve their brand encounters. Customer loyalty is driven by their degree of pleasure with La Omvi, which includes the ability to quickly access items, receive excellent customer service, and feel linked to the brand's values and identity.

Understanding the specific demands, tastes, and habits of La Omvi's target clients is critical for developing and implementing a successful omnichannel strategy. La Omvi can enhance client connections, promote repeat purchases, and eventually increase sales income by catering to their desires for convenience, personalisation, and consistency across channels.

PESTEL Analysis

1. Political Factor

Political concerns have a tremendous impact on the business environment for companies such as La Omvi. These elements include the rules, regulations, and government policies that have an impact on the fashion retail industry. Political variables in the case of La Omvi can include trade policies, taxes legislation, labor restrictions, and the political climate's stability. Changes in political leadership or movements in government policy, such as import/export laws or taxation changes, can have a direct impact on La Omvi's operations, affecting pricing and profitability. Furthermore, political stability is essential for business continuity and investor trust. A stable political environment promotes economic growth and consumer spending, which can benefit La Omvi's sales. Political insecurity or changes in government policies, on the other hand, might cause uncertainty and consequently undermine consumer confidence and purchasing behavior.

2. Economic Factor

Economic variables can have a big impact on the company's operations and sales performance. Economic fluctuations, shifts in purchasing power, and changes in customer spending patterns are all factors that can impact La Omvi's sales income and profitability. Economic variables such as recessions, inflation, or changes in disposable income can all have an impact on consumer confidence and shopping behavior, potentially leading to a reduction in consumer expenditure on fashion products. Additionally, during economic downturns, shifts in consumer tastes toward more economical options or an emphasis on critical things might have an impact on La Omvi's sales. La Omvi must monitor and analyze economic factors such as GDP growth, inflation rates, and customer mood in order to adjust its marketing strategy and pricing models.

3. Sociocultural Factor

Sociocultural elements have an important part in establishing La Omvi's commercial climate. These elements include the local population's social and cultural conventions, values, beliefs, and lifestyle preferences. Understanding sociocultural factors is critical for La Omvi to successfully position its products and services and respond to its target customers' needs and desires. The growing popularity of streetwear fashion among the younger generation is one key sociocultural aspect for La Omvi. The need for self-expression, individualism, and affinity with certain subcultures is reflected in the cultural movement toward urban streetwear aesthetics. To capitalize on this trend, La Omvi can curate a varied range of streetwear brands that correspond with its target market's cultural preferences and objectives.

4. Technological Factor

Technological factors shape the business environment for La Omvi, influencing its operations and market potential. La Omvi may face both opportunities and challenges as a result of the integration of technology in the fashion retail industry. Technological advancements, such as the rise of e-commerce platforms, smartphone applications, and social media, have changed the way shoppers discover, browse, and purchase fashion products. These technical improvements allow La Omvi to access a larger customer base and increase its business via internet channels. According to Statista, worldwide retail e-commerce sales hit 4.28 trillion US dollars in 2020 and are expected to expand further in the next years. As a result, embracing technology to generate a strong online presence and a smooth omnichannel experience might be critical for La Omvi's growth and competitiveness. On the other hand, rapid technological improvements need La Omvi to stay current and flexible to evolving technology in order to remain relevant in the business. La Omvi can obtain a competitive advantage by regularly analyzing technological trends and investing in innovative solutions such as customer relationship management (CRM) systems, inventory management software, and data analytics tools.

5. Environmental Factor

One environmental factor is the growing customer desire for environmentally friendly and sustainable fashion products. Consumers are becoming more aware of the environmental impact of the fashion business, and they are looking for labels that promote ethical sourcing, use eco-friendly materials, and employ sustainable manufacturing techniques. La Omvi should explore partnerships with sustainable fashion businesses or incorporate sustainable fashion lines into their product offers to address this concern.

Another environmental factor is the regulatory environment around environmental protection. Governments and regulatory agencies are enacting stronger rules to address challenges in the fashion sector such as waste management, carbon emissions, and pollution. To reduce its ecological impact, La Omvi must maintain compliance with these standards and proactively pursue environmentally friendly practices.

6. Legal Factor

Legal factors have a considerable impact on La Omvi's business environment. La Omvi's operations, compliance obligations, and general business strategy may be influenced by the legal framework in which it operates. The regulatory environment governing the fashion retail industry in Indonesia is a critical legal factor. This encompasses business registration, licensing, taxation, employment, intellectual property, consumer protection, and import/export limitations. Compliance with these legal standards is critical to ensuring that La Omvi's operations are legal and to avoid any potential legal concerns or penalties. Changes in legal rules, such as changes to labor laws or tax policies, can also have an impact on La Omvi's cost structure, employee relations, and profitability.

Porter's 5 Force

1. Threat of New Entrance: Mid

The fashion retail industry has variable entry barriers. The growth of online platforms has made it simpler for new entrants to establish an online presence, whereas establishing a physical store requires capital, this caused by it is rare for brands to want to work together on a consignment basis (no need for capital to spend) because there is not yet a convincing enough portfolio for brands to entrust selling their goods to retail, so to overcome this problem brands usually the brand will offer to sell products by wholesale to retail where this requires quite a large amount of capital because there is an MOQ that must be met, and the acquisition of suitable locations. However, establishing brand awareness and consumer loyalty may present obstacles.

2. Bargaining Power Suppliers: Mid

La Omvi's reliance on well-known local streetwear brands may provide these suppliers with some bargaining power. However, by carefully curating its brand portfolio and establishing strong relationships with suppliers, La Omvi can counteract this bargaining power to some extent.

3. Bargaining Power of Buyers: High

While customers have a variety of options for purchasing fashion products, La Omvi's unique status as the first fashion retail store in Cikarang, as well as its selling of local streetwear brands, can provide it with some negotiating power. However, factors such as Cikarang's tiny population and the availability of rival online and offline fashion merchants may limit La Omvi's

bargaining leverage. In order to attract and retain customers, La Omvi should focus on differentiating itself through exceptional customer service, exclusive collaborations, and personalized shopping experiences.

4. Threat of Substitute Product: Mid

Customers may examine alternative fashion outlets or companies that offer similar styles or trends, even if they are not the precise local streetwear brands represented by La Omvi. These alternatives could come from both domestic and international fashion businesses. Customers now have access to a diverse choice of fashion products from a variety of stores thanks to the growing popularity of internet shopping. Customers may prefer to shop online rather than in La Omvi's physical store, especially if they can discover identical or different products with greater convenience and lower prices. Fashion trends and tastes can change throughout time. Customers may choose substitute products that are more closely aligned with their shifting tastes if La Omvi fails to react to changing client wants or offer innovative and original products. La Omvi must differentiate itself through brand curation, customer experience, and a unique value proposition

5. Intensity of Competitive Rivalry: High

The fashion retail industry is extremely competitive, with many local and international brands vying for market share. La Omvi competes with both offline and online stores, making differentiation and outstanding customer experiences critical. Maintaining a competitive advantage requires innovation, branding, marketing, and the capacity to respond to shifting market trends.

Competitor Analysis

1. Orbis

The streetwear apparel retailer Orbis was founded in Jakarta in 2008 and is the city's oldest. Until 2012, Orbis carried clothing from international companies like Champion. Then, when local businesses started to emerge, Orbis started carrying local streetwear brands in its stores. Orbis relocated twice before settling on Jalan Panglima Polim in South Jakarta. OTSS coffee is the name of the coffee shop that Orbis currently operates inside of its store.

Orbis Jakarta has a number of competitive advantages that have helped it gain notoriety as one of Jakarta's best stores and the go-to location for street and traditional workwear as well as the most recent fashion trends. Orbis Jakarta stands apart from many other stores in Jakarta because of its initial goal to offer the local market a global assortment of fashions. Orbis gives customers access to distinctive and current styles that could not be easily found elsewhere by providing a wide variety of fashion selections from around the world. Orbis Jakarta has earned a reputation as one of Jakarta's top stores over the years. Their competitive advantage is a result of their standing and awareness among clients. Positive word-of-mouth, client loyalty, and a solid brand reputation all help Orbis stand out from its rivals and draw in new clients.

2. Zodiac

Zodiac, which opened in December 2018, is a weekday light-music pub that transforms into a small club on the weekends. Beyond the spotless soundscape of the bar, Zodiac offers a permanent retail exhibition area designed for showcases, exhibitions, and pop-up shops. Zodiac consistently seeks out new activations with various fashion labels, music collectives, international DJs, and nearby businesses. Combining the three elements music, fashion, and art that influence today's culture.

Zodiac Jakarta has a distinct advantage over rival businesses in the area due to the way that it combines music, fashion, and art. Being a bar with light music during the week and a tiny club during the weekends is how Zodiac Jakarta delivers a unique concept. Due to their adaptability, they can accommodate various audiences and preferences. Showcases, exhibitions, and pop-up stores have a place to be displayed thanks to the addition of a permanent retail exhibition area. As a result, chances for cross-promotion are created, and Zodiac can partner with fashion brands, music groups, foreign DJs, and local businesses, broadening its influence inside the neighborhood. New partnerships and activations are constantly sought for by Zodiac. They stay on the cutting edge of trends and draw in a varied audience by collaborating with fashion labels, music collectives, and international DJs. These partnerships also introduce novel experiences and occasions, making sure that clients have an incentive to come back often. The fusion of art, music, and fashion at Zodiac represents the cultural forces that define contemporary society. By fusing these components, Zodiac produces a distinctive and lively environment that connects with its target audience and adds to its competitive advantage.

3. Sonderlab

Sonderlab is an online retailer that combines national and international brands to create a diverse shopping experience. Customers may learn more about the unique histories and tales of each company thanks to the product curation, which elevates

Sonderlab to the status of a truly immersive online shopping destination.

Sonderlab's distinct strategy for doing online shopping distinguishes it from conventional e-commerce platforms, giving it a competitive advantage. By fusing national and international brands, Sonderlab distinguishes itself and gives clients a wide selection of goods to pick from. This wide variety enhances the purchasing experience by introducing clients to uncommon goods and brands that they might not otherwise find. By meticulously choosing and curating goods from diverse brands, Sonderlab's product curation enhances the buying experience. Customers who value learning about the origins of the products they buy may be drawn to Sonderlab's selection of merchandise since it conveys a feeling of authenticity and storytelling. In contrast to rivals who may only concentrate on regional or mainstream products, Sonderlab distinguishes itself by carrying national and international brands. Due to its uniqueness, Sonderlab is able to serve a larger range of customers and draw in those seeking a more distinctive and global shopping experience.

Table 1. Competitive Analysis

Key Aspect	Orbis	Zodiac	Sonderlab
Product	Unisex streetwear apparel	Unisex streetwear apparel, pubs	Streetwear apparel, men's wear, women's wear, accessories, home goods
Price	Start from Rp89.000 - Rp2.000.000	Start From Rp150.000 - Rp 1.500.000	Start from Rp99.000 - Rp5.299.000
Place	Multichannel - Offline store - Website Orbisjkt.com	Multichannel Offline store Website Zodiacjakarta.com	Website Sonderlab.com
Promotion	- Digital marketing - Campaign - Brand activation - Seasonal event - Brand collaboration - Community engagement - Media publication	- Digital marketing - Campaign - Brand activation - Weekly event - Brand collaboration - Community engagement - Endorsement - Media publication	- Digital marketing - Pop up store - Brand collaboration - Customer engagement - Endorsement - Media publication

Internal Analysis

Current STP

Segmentation

Table 2. Segmentation

Geographic	Country	Indonesia
	City	Cikarang, Jabodetabek
	Density	Urban, Suburban
Demography	Age	18-40
	Gender	Men, Women
	Occupation	Student, Employee, Entrepreneur
	Expenditure on each purchase	> Rp150.000
Psychographic	Status social	Middle Class and Affluent Consumer (MAC)
Behavior	Trend	Follow the latest fashion trends
	Prestige	Like to use a brand that can increase social status
	Quality	Concern for quality

La Omvi segmentation is divided into four variables, namely demographic, geographic, psychographic and behavioral. The demographic segment is taken based on the results of a market survey conducted on 143 respondents and the database owned by La Omvi. The targeted psychographic segmentation is the MAC social class (middle class and affluent consumer) or a mix of middle class and affluent social classes. Currently, it is predicted that each year there will be 8 to 9 million new middle class people.

Targeting

Table 3 Targeting

	Product Type
	Retail
Country	Indonesia
City	Cikarang
Density	Urban
Age	18-40
Gender	Men, Women
Occupation	Student, Employee, Entrepreneur

ositioning

For fashion enthusiasts, La Omvi is Cikarang's first fashion retailer, presenting a carefully chosen collection of well-known local streetwear brands while actively promoting creativity and aiding educational projects in the fashion sector.

Current Marketing Mix 4P

1. Product

La Omvi's main product is providing products from well-known local and global streetwear brands. The brands in La Omvi have gone through curation in order to maintain the consistency of the brand image as a streetwear fashion retailer. The curation is carried out in terms of concept, history and market. In addition, La Omvi also creates and supports events related to education and creativity in the fashion sector.

2. Price

The product prices offered by La Omvi vary, starting from Rp. 79,000 to Rp. 2,400,000 depending on the brand and product category. The best-selling category is t-shirts, with an average price of Rp 170,000 to Rp 999,000. The most expensive category is the hoodie, with selling prices starting from Rp 300,000 to Rp 2,400,000. The product price set by La Omvi uses a consignment agreement with the brand owner, where La Omvi takes a profit of 30% of the price of each product entrusted to sell to La Omvi.

3. Place

To this day, La Omvi focuses its sales through offline stores, so that more products sell well through its offline stores. The offline store location is at Jl. Industri Utara IV No.8, Mekarmukti, Kec. Cikarang Utara, Bekasi, Jawa Barat 17530. La omvi can also be found on several social media, such as Instagram and Youtube.

4. Promotion

La Omvi does marketing using online and offline media.

Online Promotion:

1) Instagram & Facebook Ads

Instagram & Facebook ads are used because the features of Facebook Ads can accommodate to reach a more specific market. La Omvi uses Facebook ads to market store information, products and current discount and promo information.

2) Endorsement

La Omvi uses an endorsement strategy by looking for micro influencers who have influence both on social media and in the real world. Based on the results of interviews with the owner, due to limited marketing budgets, La Omvi takes a personal approach to target micro influencers, so La Omvi only needs to send the product to these micro influencers and does not pay for the available rate cards.

Offline Promotion:

1) Discount & Bundling

La Omvi provides regular discounts every Eid and year-end. The discount given varies from 5% to 50%. As for the bundling promo program, La Omvi provides discounts for customers who want to buy bundled products.

2) Sponsorship & Collaboration

- La Omvi funded coffee cups for 5 well-known coffee shops in Cikarang, and packaged them into a video campaign aimed at inviting young people in Cikarang to dare to be creative and to change the stigma about an industrial city.
- La Omvi partners with local coffee shops to create specialty coffee products under the name La Omvi.

3) Artist Series

La Omvi collaborated with several well-known illustrators in Jakarta and finally, La Omvi collaborated with a Japanese illustrator, Amy Brereton.

VRIO Analysis

Table 4. VRIO Analysis

Resources	V	R	I	O	Impact
Brand Image	✓	✓	✓	✓	Strong Competitive Advantage
Curation Expertise	✓	✓	✓	✓	Strong Competitive Advantage
Community engagement	✓	✓	✓	✓	Strong Competitive Advantage
Location & Events	✓	✓	✓	✓	Strong Competitive Advantage
Man Power	✓	X	X	✓	Contemporary Competitive Advantage
Distribution	✓	X	X	X	Weak Competitive Advantage

1. Valuable

La Omvi's unique position as Cikarang's first fashion retail store, as well as its strong ties with well-known local streetwear businesses, provide vital resources. This enables La Omvi to offer in-demand products and cater to the specific interests of its target market, providing them a competitive advantage.

2. Rare

La Omvi has a unique capacity to curate content by analyzing brands based on concept, history, and market. It enables them to uphold a consistent brand identity as a retailer of streetwear apparel and to provide clients a carefully curated selection of goods. Competitors find it difficult to replicate this knowledge.

3. Imitable

La Omvi has made a name for itself as the first clothing retailer in Cikarang over the years. It is challenging to replicate their brand identity and reputation as a leading streetwear fashion site. It would take time and effort to establish a similar degree of awareness and confidence in the market.

4. Organized

La Omvi's dedication to developing and sponsoring events relating to fashion education and creativity, along with its strategic position in the Jababeka, Cikarang, show their concerted efforts to take advantage of their resources and potential. They may draw people, build brand exposure, and encourage customer involvement by utilizing their location and events.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

- First Retail in Cikarang: La Omvi has a competitive advantage by positioning itself as a pioneer in the area by virtue of being the first fashion retail store in Cikarang.
- Curated Selection: La Omvi's focus on curating well-known local streetwear brands helps maintain a consistent brand image and attracts customers looking for unique and trendy products.
- Location: Being located in the Jababeka area of Cikarang provides La Omvi with visibility and accessibility, potentially attracting a larger customer base.
- Events: La Omvi's commitment to organizing events related to fashion education and creativity enhances its brand image and helps build a loyal community of fashion enthusiasts.

Weaknesses

- Small Target Market: The small population of Cikarang may limit the possible consumer base for La Omvi, making it difficult to increase sales.
- Limited Operating History: La Omvi's establishment in 2020 means it has a relatively short operating history compared to more established competitors. This lack of history might make it more challenging to build trust and credibility among

customers.

Opportunities

- Growing Streetwear Market: The popularity of streetwear fashion is on the rise globally, presenting an opportunity for La Omvi to tap into this growing market segment and attract a dedicated customer base.
- Online Sales Growth: La Omvi now has the chance to reach more customers through an integrated omnichannel strategy and extend its reach beyond its physical store thanks to the increased popularity of online purchasing.
- Collaboration and Partnership: By organizing collaborative events and participating in promotional activities, working with regional designers, influencers, and organizations can increase brand visibility and draw in new clients.

Threats

- Competitive Market: The fashion retail industry is highly competitive, and La Omvi may face competition from both local and international fashion retailers in the area.
- Economic Conditions: Economic fluctuations or downturns can impact consumer spending on fashion items, affecting La Omvi's sales and growth prospects.
- Online Shopping: The growth of e-commerce and online shopping platforms poses a threat to traditional brick-and-mortar stores like La Omvi, necessitating a strong online presence and effective digital marketing strategies.

Business Solution

TOWS Analysis

Table 5. TOWS Matrix

	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
	S1 First Retail in Cikarang S2 Curated Selection S3 Events	W1 Small Target Market W2 Limited Operating History
OPPORTUNITIES O1 Growing Streetwear Market O2 Online Sales Growth O3 Collaboration & Partnership	- Strengthen collaborations with local designers and emerging fashion brands to offer exclusive products and unique collections. (S2, O3) - Capitalize on being the first fashion retail store in Cikarang to build brand awareness and attract a loyal customer base. (S1, O1, O2) - Expand the store's reach beyond Cikarang through online platforms, to extend its market reach beyond the physical store. (S2, O2)	- Investing in robust e-commerce capabilities and digital marketing strategies to effectively compete with online retailers. (W1, O2) - Use its community-building efforts and events to create an engaging offline experience and encourage consumer loyalty. (W1, O1) - Build Trust and credibility through Omnichannel Approach. (W2, O2)
THREATS T1 Competitive Market T2 Online Shop	- Stay updated with changing consumer behavior and evolving fashion trends to adapt the omnichannel strategy accordingly and maintain a competitive edge. (S2, T1)	- Enhance the online presence and omnichannel capabilities of La Omvi to effectively compete with online streetwear retailers. (W1, T1, T2) - Implement marketing campaigns to enhance brand recognition and awareness in the local market, leveraging social media, influencer collaborations, and targeted online advertising. (W1, T1, T2) - Identify and address potential economic challenges by offering competitive pricing, periodic promotions, and strategic partnerships to enhance value for customers. (W1, T1)

SO Strategies

La Omvi's approach of expanding collaborations with local designers and developing fashion businesses is a big strength. La Omvi may offer special products and unique collections that set it apart from competitors by collaborating with these designers and businesses. This strategy not only improves the store's product selections, but also strengthens its reputation as a destination for trendy and sought-after fashion items. Furthermore, La Omvi's position as the first fashion retail store in Cikarang is a significant asset that may be used to increase brand awareness and establish a devoted client base. This positioning as a market pioneer provides La Omvi with a competitive advantage and can lead to long-term consumer loyalty and support. La Omvi could explore expanding its reach outside Cikarang by having an internet presence to strengthen its market position. The store can expand its market reach by using online platforms to contact customers in different locations who may not have physical access to the store. This omnichannel strategy enables La Omvi to reach a larger consumer base and enhance sales potential. La Omvi can increase its market position, attract a larger client base, and drive sales growth by combining and capitalizing on these assets.

ST Strategy

La Omvi may identify developing trends, preferences, and purchase habits by staying up to current on changing customer behavior. This data may then be utilized to improve its omnichannel strategy and ensure that the proper products, services, and experiences are available through the most appropriate channels. For example, if La Omvi's target customers are increasingly interested in online buying, the company can invest in strengthening its e-commerce platform, improving the user experience, and

providing simple online purchasing choices.

WO Strategies

- La Omvi can effectively compete with online merchants by investing in robust e-commerce capabilities and digital marketing strategies. This includes creating a user-friendly and secure online platform for users to explore and buy products, as well as employing digital marketing tactics to increase online presence and reach a larger client base. La Omvi can tap into the growing trend of online purchasing and expand its market reach beyond the physical store by embracing e-commerce.
- La Omvi can use its community-building initiatives and events to provide clients with an engaging offline experience. La Omvi can differentiate itself from internet stores and attract clients who appreciate the social component of shopping by hosting fashion-related events, engaging with local designers, and establishing a feeling of community. By providing a unique and memorable purchasing experience, this method can assist establish consumer loyalty and drive repeat business.
- Through an omnichannel approach, La Omvi can concentrate on establishing trust and confidence. La Omvi can give a consistent and cohesive brand experience to clients by smoothly integrating its online and offline channels. This includes ensuring that products, pricing, and promotions are consistent across all channels, as well as offering dependable customer service and after-sales support. La Omvi can improve its reputation and acquire a competitive advantage in the market by providing a trustworthy and reliable buying experience.

WT Strategies

Several strategic initiatives can be implemented to handle La Omvi's Weaknesses and Threats. To begin, improving online visibility and building omnichannel capabilities are critical for effectively competing with online streetwear stores. This can be accomplished by creating a user-friendly and visually appealing e-commerce website, maximizing search engine exposure, and ensuring seamless integration of online and physical channels. La Omvi can attract and retain a larger consumer base by providing a convenient and consistent buying experience across numerous platforms.

Additionally, establishing targeted marketing campaigns is critical for increasing brand recognition and awareness in the local market. Using social media channels, engaging with influencers, and deploying targeted online advertising can successfully reach and enhance visibility. These tactics aid in the development of a strong brand identity, the engagement of potential customers, and the differentiation of La Omvi from its competitors.

New STP Formulation

Segmenting

Geographic

Targeting the locals in Cikarang, where La Omvi is, and also Increase the geographic scope of the project beyond Cikarang to surrounding regions like Bekasi, Karawang, or Jakarta as well as other significant cities like Makassar, Bali, Surabaya, Lampung, and Balikpapan. There are more people in these areas, and they provide potential clients who might be interested in La Omvi's goods. Increase the accessibility and reach of La Omvi's offers by utilizing social media campaigns, targeted internet advertising, and collaborations with delivery services.

Demography

Targeting college student and young professional who are interested in fashion and are more likely to use social media and online platforms. This group is more open to internet marketing initiatives and frequently searches out streetwear fashion. This category can be enticed to engage with the omnichannel experience by providing comfortable online shopping alternatives with quick delivery and simple returns.

Behaviour

Target those that have a keen interest in fashion, follow current trends, and actively look for high-quality, fashionable clothing. customers who favor internet buying for its accessibility and convenience. Targeted internet advertising, email marketing, and participation in social media can all be used to reach these customers, who feel at ease making purchases through digital channels. Engage clients who are tech-savvy and early adopters of new platforms for digital commerce. To suit their interests, provide seamless and practical online shopping experiences, individualized recommendations, and mobile-friendly user interfaces

Table 6. New STP Formulation

Geographic	Country	Indonesia
	City	Cikarang, Jabodetabek, Makassar, Bali, Surabaya
	Density	Urban, Suburban
Demography	Age	18-35
	Gender	Men, Women
	Occupation	College student, Young Professional
	Expenditure on each purchase	> Rp150.000
Psychographic	Status social	Middle Class and Affluent Consumer (MAC)
Behavior	Trend	Follow the latest fashion trends
	Prestige	Like to use a brand that can increase social status
	Quality	Concern for quality
	Tech	Tech savvy shoppers

Targeting

Targeting students and young professionals who are more likely to be early adopters of fashion trends and have disposable income for fashion purchases who are interested in streetwear brands that are living in urban city who prefer online shopping or have shown an inclination towards e-commerce or website platforms.

Positioning

La Omvi as a fashion-forward retailer that offers a seamless and immersive shopping experience both online and offline. Emphasize the convenience, variety, and accessibility of shopping through multiple channels, showcasing La Omvi's commitment to delivering a holistic and trendsetting experience.

Marketing Mix Formulation

Product

Based on the analysis data, La Omvi must focus on streetwear products that have various variations while prioritizing product quality. The following are brands that are expected to be present at La Omvi based on the survey results:

1. Paradise Youth Club
Paradise Youth Club (PYC) offers a complete variety of products, from tops, bottoms to accessories with unique design. The material used by PYC is heavyweight cotton, which is the best quality material in the cotton class.
2. A More Mindful Era
A More Mindful Era is a Jakarta-based brand whose designs emphasize liberty. It was the product of imagination, meticulous attention to detail, and a creative explosion. We obtain our ideas, patterns, and preferences from a wide variety of sources. From basic concepts to diverse contexts that defy the imagination. AMME consists of individuals who fell in love with the enchantment of patterns, color combinations, and odd images. This affection has evolved into a desire to revitalize the local apparel scene.

And other brands that you want to be present at La Omvi, such as Mankind, Pacific Place, Dominate dan Deva State.

Price

La Omvi partnership with local streetwear brands with a consignment and wholesale system so that La Omvi benefits from the special prices given as the brand's official retailer. With this, La Omvi can provide a lower selling price than product prices on the brand's official website, competitor stores, or other e-commerce.

Place

Figure 2 Omnichannel Framework

Based on the Journal written by Payne, Peltier & Barger (2017), La Omvi can use a variety of omnichannel techniques to strengthen its competitive position and generate sales income. To begin, it is critical to integrate online and offline channels. La Omvi can create an easy-to-use e-commerce website where customers can explore and buy products, with the option of in-store pickup or home delivery. Customers may enjoy a consistent brand and shopping experience across several channels thanks to this seamless connection.

La Omvi can also take advantage of mobile technologies by designing a specific website. To encourage repeat purchases, the app can include tailored suggestions, unique offers, and a loyalty program. This channel allows La Omvi to reach out to clients on the go and improve their shopping experience.

Using social media sites is another excellent method. La Omvi may actively engage with customers on social media channels such as Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok, displaying new arrivals, behind-the-scenes content, and client testimonials. This increases brand awareness, traffic to online and offline stores, and customer loyalty.

La Omvi might also explore collaborations with complimentary businesses or influencers to broaden its reach and target new client categories. Joint promotional efforts, co-branded product releases, and cross-marketing initiatives are examples of collaborations. These collaborations increase brand awareness, attract new clients, and generate conversation about La Omvi's goods.

1. Physical Store

Ensure that the offline and online channels are seamlessly integrated. This includes synchronizing inventory management systems to provide accurate online and in-store product availability information.

2. Website

Integrate features that bridge the gap between online and offline purchasing. Offer in-store return, exchange, and retrieval options for online orders. Display real-time inventory data to prevent consumer dissatisfaction caused by out-of-stock items.

Figure 3. La Omvi's Website Progress

3. Digital Advertising

Promote the online store using a variety of marketing channels, such as social media, email marketing, and in-store signage. Highlight the advantages of purchasing online, such as a larger selection of products, greater convenience, and access to special offers. Promote the offline store through online channels by highlighting in-store events, exclusive in-store experiences, and personalized grooming services.

Utilizing digital media as a promotional tool and also a place to sell. The latest features provided by social media today are able to provide this facility, such as Instagram with an Instagram shop, this feature allows business owners to upload photos on Instagram feeds and add product links to be able to check out directly on the brand's website.

Figure 4. Instagram Shop

Source: Aries Arise, 2023

4. Social Media

Create high-quality, visually enticing content that resonates with the intended audience. This includes showcasing the most recent fashion trends, highlighting new arrivals, showcasing customer testimonials, and providing insights behind the scenes of the brand's activities. Ensure that the brand's identity, values, and unique selling factors are effectively conveyed in the account profiles and visually represented through the account images.

5. CRM

Collect comprehensive consumer data via multiple touchpoints, such as the website, social media platforms, and in-store interactions. This information should include consumer contact details, purchase history, browsing behavior, preferences, and demographic information. Invest in a robust CRM system that integrates online and offline channels. The software should offer a centralized database for storing user data and facilitate communication across multiple channels. Analyze the collected customer data in order to segment the customer base according to demographics, purchasing behavior, preferences, and other relevant factors. This segmentation enables more targeted and personalized marketing efforts. Utilize consumer data and segmentation to personalize communications across multiple channels. Send targeted email campaigns, SMS messages, and push notifications that promote relevant products, discounts, and offers to specific consumer segments. Integrate loyalty

programs into the omnichannel CRM strategy in order to reward and incentivize consumer loyalty. Provide loyal consumers with exclusive discounts, early access to new products, and personalized offers.

Promotion

Integrated Marketing Communication

IMC is a strategic approach that aligns and coordinates numerous marketing communication aspects and channels in order to present a consistent and coherent message to target audiences. In order to develop a smooth and effective communication strategy, IMC entails the integration and synergy of marketing, public relations, sales promotion, direct marketing, personal selling, and other communication instruments. Delivering a consistent message across several touchpoints and interacting with customers in a significant and lasting way are the objectives of IMC, which are to increase brand awareness, generate brand equity, and create a positive customer experience (Kumar, 2017).

Based on the definition above and the results of interviews with customers and industry experts, La Omvi's integrated marketing communication (IMC) approach would combine multiple marketing communication aspects and channels in order to convey a coherent and consistent brand message and enhance customer engagement.

- Make sure that the brand messaging is consistent throughout all of the communication channels, including the website, social media, advertising, and in-store promotions. The messaging should emphasize La Omvi's unique position as the top supplier of regional streetwear brands and the value it brings to customers in terms of style, quality, and fashion expertise. Create advertising content that can refer to a call to action, by combining advertising media such as social media with a place to sell.
- Offer in-store pickup for online purchases, or advertise online-only deals and discounts that may be redeemed in-store. Keep your logo and product information consistent across all platforms to give your customers a seamless online-offline integration experience.
- Based on consumer preferences and purchase history, implement customized communication strategies, such as email marketing and targeted advertising.
- Encourage customers to provide comments and evaluations on social media platforms, and the La Omvi website.

CONCLUSION

The research proposed a comprehensive omnichannel strategy for La Omvi to increase sales. This strategy encompasses integrating online and offline channels, enhancing the online shopping experience, leveraging social media platforms, and fostering customer engagement through personalized marketing initiatives. The goal is to provide a seamless and convenient shopping experience for customers across various touchpoints

The study offered a detailed execution strategy for the recommended marketing approach. This strategy entails activities such as enhancing La Omvi's website, launching social media campaigns, cooperating with influencers, providing personalized suggestions, and delivering special online deals. The strategy's effectiveness must be monitored and analyzed in order to make required adjustments for continual improvement, according to the plan. La Omvi's proposed omnichannel strategy involves leveraging digital platforms, optimizing the online purchasing experience, personalizing communication, and integrating the physical store and online channels seamlessly. By employing this strategy, La Omvi will be able to expand its market presence, attract new customers, and strengthen its relationships with existing ones.

Finally, the research findings emphasize the importance of La Omvi developing an omnichannel approach to address the challenges given by the internal and external environments. The proposed approach, backed up by an execution plan, intends to improve the customer experience, broaden La Omvi's market reach, and eventually increase revenues. To achieve long-term success in the competitive fashion retail market, it is recommended that La Omvi executes the proposed plan while continuously monitoring its performance and changing as needed.

REFERENCES

1. Armstrong, Gary T. and Gary Armstrong. 2021. Principles of Marketing Global Edition 18th Ed., Pearson
2. Badan Pusat Statistik, 2022. PDB Industri Tekstil dan Pakaian Jadi. <https://dataindonesia.id/sector-riil/detail/industri-tekstil-kembali-melesat-1374-pada-kuartal-ii2022>.
3. Bekraf, 2019. Laporan Kinerja Badan Ekonomi Kreatif Tahun 2019. Jakarta; Kementerian Pariwisata dan Ekonomi Kreatif.

4. Berman, B., Evans J. R., & Chatterjee, P. 2018. Retail Management: A Strategic Approach 13th Ed. Upper Sadle River, Nj. Prentice Hall.
5. Buttler, Francis A., 2019. Customer Relationship Management: Concepts and Technology. Routledge
6. Berman, B., Evans J. R., & Chatterjee, P. 2018. Retail Management: A Strategic Approach
7. Chen, I. J., & Popovich, K. (2003). Understanding Customer Relationship Management (CRM); People, Process and Technology. Business Process Management Journal, 9, 672-688.
8. Chevalier, S. (2022, September 21). Global retail e-commerce sales 2026. Statista. Retrieved February 20, 2023, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/379046/worldwide-retail-e-commerce-sales/>.
9. CNBC Indonesia, 2019. Gairah Industri Fashion Indonesia. Retrieved February 20 2023, from <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/lifestyle/20190712155341-35-84555/gairah-industri-fashion-indonesia>.
10. Creswell, J. W. (2014). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. SAGE Publications.
11. Ellis-Chadwick, F., & Chaffey, D. (2019). Digital Marketing. Pearson.
12. J.A. Smith, P. Flower and M. Larkin (2009), Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research
13. Glitzmedia, 2020. Kisah Balik Sejarah Kehadiran Streetwear yang Kian Melejit. Retrieved February 20, 2023 from <https://glitzmedia.co/post/leisure/journal/kilas-balik-sejarah-kehadiran-streetwear-yang-kian-melejit>.
14. Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., & Hoskisson, R. E. (2015). Strategic Management: Concepts and Cases: Competitiveness and Globalization. Cengage Learning.
15. Hypebeast, 2019. Streetwear Global Market Research. Retrieved February, 20, 2023 from <https://strategyand.hypebeast.com/streetwear-report>.
16. Juaneda, Emma., Mosquera, Ana., & Murilio, Yolanda S. (2016). Omnichannel Customer Behavior: Key Drivers of Technology Acceptance and Use and Their Effects on Purchase Intention. Retrieved on May 31, 2023 from <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2016.01117/full>
17. Kementrian Perindustrian Republik Indonesia, 2020. Indonesia Berpotensi Lahirkan Banyak Brand Global. <https://kemenperin.go.id/artikel/21981/Indonesia-Berpotensi-Lahirkan-Banyak-Global-Brand>.
18. Kim, Jung Hwan, Kim Minjeong, & Lennon, Sharon J. 2018. Effects of Web Site Atmospheric on Consumer Responses: Music and Product Presentation. Retrieved on May 31, 2023 from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235297539_Effects_of_web_site_atmospherics_on_consumer_responses_Music_and_product_presentation
19. Kompas, 2021. Mengenal Streetwear, Tren Gaya Fashion Jalanan yang Naik Kelas. <https://www.kompas.com/parapuan/read/533028071/mengenal-streetwear-tren-gaya-fashion-jalanan-yang-naik-kelas>.
20. Kompas, 2021. Mengenal Streetwear, Tren Gaya Fashion Jalanan yang Naik Kelas. <https://www.kompas.com/parapuan/read/533028071/mengenal-streetwear-tren-gaya-fashion-jalanan-yang-naik-kelas>.
21. Kumar, N. 2017. Integrated Marketing Communication. www.himpub.com
22. Kumar, Ranjit. 2011. Research Methodology 3rd Edition, London, SAGE Publications Ltd.
23. Kartajaya, Hermawan & Setiawan, Iwan. (2015). WOW Marketing. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
24. Lester, Jr. Frank K. 2005. On the theoretical, conceptual, and philosophical foundations for research in mathematics education. ZDM, 37(6), 457-467. DOI:10.1007/BF02655854.
25. Li, Hosuang & Kannan, P.K. (2014). Attributing Conversions in a Multichannel Online Marketing Environment: An Empirical Model and a Field Experiment. Journal of Marketing Research, 51(1): 40–56.
26. Liehr, P. and Smith, M. J. 1999. Middle range theory: Spinning research and practice to create knowledge for the new millennium. Advances in Nursing Science, 21(4), 81-91. DOI: 10.1097/00012272-199906000-00011.
27. Payne, E. M., Peltier, J. W., & Barger, V. A. (2017). Omni-channel marketing, integrated marketing communications, and consumer engagement: A research agenda. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316570822_Omni-channel_marketing_integrated_marketing_communications_and_consumer_engagement_A_research_agenda.
28. Pojok Satu, 2022. Jumlah Penduduk Kabupaten Bekasi Bertambah 100 Ribu Jiwa, Kebanyakan Pendatang. Retrieved June 10, 2023 from <https://bekasi.pojoksatu.id/baca/jumlah-penduduk-kabupaten-bekasi-bertambah-100-ribu-jiwa-kebanyakan-pendatang>.

29. Ramanathan, R., & Ramanathan U. (2017). A conceptual framework for examining the antecedents and consequences of retail store ambience. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*.
30. Rothamel, F. T., 2021. *Strategic Management 5th Ed.*, New York, NY: Mc Graw-Hill.
31. Verhoef, Peter C., Kannan, P. K., Inman, J. J. Jeffrey, 2015. From Multi-Channel Retailing to Omni-Channel Retailin. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267269215_From_Multichannel_to_Omnichannel_Retailing_Review_of_the_Literature_and_Calls_for_Research
32. Vice, 2018. Alasan Streetwear Yang Dulunya Cuma Digemari Skater Kini Jadi Buruan ABG Tajir. Retrived February 20, 2023 from <https://www.vice.com/id/article/yw5gz7/alasan-streetwear-yang-dulunya-cuma-digemari-skater-kini-jadi-buruan-abg-tajir>.

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